

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Dynamic Movement Primitives in Constrained Environments: Teaching Control Policies Through Repeated Demonstrations

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ABSTRACT Enabling robots to learn from few demonstrations is a crucial step toward task automation. This paper addresses a key challenge in robotic learning from demonstration: developing adaptable, constraint-aware systems that learn from a limited number of demonstrations, infer task-specific geometrical constraints autonomously, and ensure trajectory adherence to these constraints while remaining accessible to non-expert users. The proposed methodology integrates automatic task-constraint extraction from teleoperated demonstrations with a novel sigmoidal coupling term (SIG-CDMP) to enforce spatial constraints within Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs). By analyzing variability in demonstrations, the framework defines a tolerance zone for robot motion and ensures that generated trajectories remain within these bounds, even when adapting to new initial or goal positions. The efficacy of this approach is validated in two real-world industrial applications—sterility testing in pharmaceutical industry and cable wiring in electric vehicle batteries—demonstrating negligible increases in computational cost and smooth, constraint-compliant trajectories. By integrating task-constraint extraction and enforcement, this approach advances the development of constraint-aware robotic systems that learn from repeated demonstrations to teach control policies respecting inferred geometrical constraints, paving the way for safe and reliable task automation in complex environments.

INDEX TERMS Artificial potential fields, dynamic movement primitives, few-shot learning, learning from demonstration, robots, workspace constraints.

I. INTRODUCTION

As robotic systems become more integrated into industrial, domestic, and assistive environments, the need for robots to learn and adapt autonomously has grown significantly. While modern robots incorporate different types of sensors, making them more intelligent, humans still need to define the tasks to be performed. Different modalities are available

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for transferring the task description to the robot, such as: a) manual programming through the interface tooling provided by the manufacturer [1], [2]; b) advanced control schemes specially designed and adjusted by experts, using ROS and high level control schemes like skill framework [3]; or c) learning by demonstrations, where the robotic system is designed to learn the task from a human execution [4].

Traditional methods for teaching robots, such as manual programming, offer precision and control but often require technical expertise and are not well-suited for tasks that

change frequently. Similarly, advanced control frameworks based on predefined skills are effective in highly structured settings but can become cumbersome when adapting to new or changing conditions. These limitations highlight the growing importance of Learning from Demonstrations (LfD), a family of methods that allows non-expert users to teach robots new tasks through intuitive interactions. This approach is particularly valuable in industries with small-batch production or high product diversity, where custom automation can be complex and not cost-effective.

The LfD pipeline typically involves three steps: (1) demonstration collection, (2) model training, and (3) trajectory generation. The quality and feasibility of LfD depend heavily on the method used to collect human demonstrations. Common approaches include sensor-based demonstrations (which require complex human-robot mapping), kinesthetic teaching (where the robot is physically guided, risking sensor interference), and teleoperation (remote control via haptic devices) [4]. Teleoperation is particularly advantageous in hazardous or sterile environments, as it eliminates direct human-robot contact while enabling precise and safe data collection.

A critical design consideration is the number of demonstrations required. While more examples improve accuracy, they also increase user workload. An ideal system minimizes the number of demonstrations while capturing task variability and constraints, particularly in settings requiring rapid retraining [5].

Another critical aspect is the selection of the learning algorithm. Historically, probabilistic techniques such as HMMs (Hidden Markov Models) [6] and GMMs (Gaussian Mixture Models) [7], [8] have been widely used for robotic motion learning. These techniques offer a flexible representation of the trajectory, with a moderate data requirement, typically in the range of tens of examples. With the advent of deep learning, models capable of learning from large volumes of data have been developed, which improves accuracy but also increases complexity and computational requirements. At the other end, there are methods that can learn a task from a single demonstration, such as DMPs (Dynamic Movement Primitives) [9], which is particularly useful in contexts where time and resources are limited.

However, although ideal from the user perspective, relying on a single demonstration for the model training could carry risks during the trajectory reproduction. Indeed, it is impossible to deduce from a unique reference the possible spatial constraints of the task to reproduce. Therefore, if the trajectory generated by the learning algorithm deviates from the demonstration, it cannot be guaranteed that the robot will remain within the authorized area. In contrast, with multiple demonstrations, the learning system can deduce from the observed variability the critical areas of the path. Therefore, exploring learning from a reasonable number of demonstrations, limiting the associated user workload, and

ensuring an adequate task description at the same time is proposed.

The trained model should be able to use the task constraints derived from the variability analysis in order to generate curves that meet them. It is essential that the system has the ability to adapt its generated outcome if the constraints are not met in a fast, reliable, and smooth manner without retraining. DMPs have the ability to encode and reproduce complex, time-dependent movement patterns in a compact and generalizable form, making them a powerful tool for robot learning from demonstrations. DMPs are particularly well-suited for robotic applications due to their inherent flexibility, stability, and adaptability to changes in boundary conditions. They allow the system to generate smooth, dynamically consistent trajectories by learning a dynamical system that can be modulated in real-time to adjust for variations. This capability is frequently used to adjust the start or goal position, and indeed the model is able to adapt to these changes while keeping the same motion dynamics. Nevertheless, this adaptation does not ensure that the system would respect the spatial constraints deduced from the demonstrations. To address this limitation, it becomes necessary to incorporate additional mechanisms that allow the robot to respect the task constraints, even when boundary conditions change.

DMPs' natural rollouts can be modified incorporating a coupling term. Artificial Potential Fields (APFs) [10] are well-known methods for guiding motion while avoiding constraint violations. They are a cost-effective solution for implementing adaptive and constraint-aware robot motion, as they require minimal computational resources and can be easily integrated as a coupling term into the DMP formulation. As shown in [11], the combination of DMPs and APFs is frequently employed to enhance obstacle avoidance while maintaining the generalization properties of DMPs. However, the spatial constraints inherent to the task are often not explicitly considered in existing approaches. This limitation motivates the need for a system that bridges the gap between DMPs' adaptability and explicit constraint enforcement.

This paper addresses one of the current challenges in the field of robotic learning from demonstration: developing adaptable, constraint-aware systems that learn from a limited number of demonstrations, infer task-specific geometrical constraints autonomously, and ensure trajectory adherence to these constraints while remaining accessible to non-expert users. By integrating task constraint extraction and constraint enforcement, this approach advances the development of intuitive and collaborative robotic systems for real-world applications.

This document is structured as follows. Section II analyses the related state of the art. Section III presents the proposed automatic task constraint extraction strategy. Section IV describes the novel methodology to teach control policies

to the robot to maintain the generated trajectory within the task tolerance zone. It also compares the proposed approach with related solutions of the literature. Section V shows the experimental results in two real-world case studies. Finally, section VI provides a summary of the main conclusions of this work.

II. RELATED WORK

A. LFD PARADIGM STRUCTURE

The process of Learning from Demonstration is typically structured in three distinct phases, as illustrated in Figure 1. In the first phase, *data collection*, a human operator performs the task multiple times. The second phase, *model learning*, involves processing the collected demonstrations to extract a generalizable representation of the task. Finally, in the *trajectory generation* phase, the learned model is used to synthesize new, executable trajectories that the robot can perform.

FIGURE 1. Overview of the (A) Learning from Demonstration (LFD) project structure, consisting of three main stages: B) Human-Robot Data Collection, where motion data is gathered from human demonstrations; C) Model Learning, where a dynamic model (e.g., DMP) is learned from the collected data; and D) Trajectory Generation and Constraint Enforcement, where the learned model is used to generate trajectories that are adapted to environmental constraints.

B. HUMAN-ROBOT DATA COLLECTION

From the human-robot data collection perspective, each existing technique has its own advantages and limitations. Sensor-based demonstrations are particularly comfortable for humans as the sensors are placed on their own bodies, but they require complex mappings between the human body and the robot's arm movements [12]. Kinesthetic demonstrations consist of manually guiding the robot's gripper and joints to perform the desired manipulation [13]. In this case, the robot's movements are directly recorded so that the mapping problem disappears. But when guiding the robot, interaction forces sensed by the robot can be distorted due to the human touching the robot's joints [4]. In teleoperated demonstrations, a haptic device is used to command robot's movements remotely. This avoids both the mapping issues and the interference with the sensors mounted on the robot [4]. This makes teleoperation particularly suitable for applications that demand high precision, remote execution, or strict environmental control, such as those encountered in hazardous industrial settings, medical robotics, or sterile environments where direct human-robot physical interaction is either impractical, unsafe, or undesirable. By enabling

the operator to control the robot from a safe distance using intuitive haptic interfaces, teleoperation ensures both operational accuracy and safety, making it a preferred method in scenarios where direct physical guidance is not feasible or where contamination risks must be minimized.

C. MODEL LEARNING IN LFD

Once the task has been demonstrated, the selection of an appropriate learning strategy aligned with the requirements of the scenario is a crucial step to achieve the desired performance and adaptability. A range of different methods are available in the literature for this purpose, which can be categorized in cost and rewards learning, plan learning, and policy learning techniques [4].

Optimization [14] and reinforcement-learning (RL) [15] techniques (which fall under the cost and rewards learning) often require a significant amount of demonstrations for the system to be adequately trained, which can be time-consuming and impractical in many real-world scenarios. Policy learning plans, such as trajectory and force learning methods [7], [16], [17], on the contrary can learn from fewer demonstrations. This is particularly useful in applications where demonstrations are scarce, expensive, or difficult to obtain. In contrast, novel deep learning techniques such as graph neural networks [18] are not limited to a single category and are commonly used across cost/reward learning, planning, and policy learning. However, similar to RL, these approaches often demand extensive training datasets and computational resources, making them ill-suited for scenarios where physical experimentation is limited.

Probabilistic methods such as Hidden Markov Models (HMM) [16], Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) combined with Gaussian Mixture Regression (GMR) [7], are alternative strategies for motion modeling. However, they face several limitations in robotics applications. HMMs, for example, struggle with temporal scaling—adjusting the duration of a learned movement without retraining—while GMM&GMR can suffer from the curse of dimensionality, degrading performance as the complexity of the task increases. Moreover, neither method inherently guarantees stability, a critical requirement for safe and reliable robotic control.

Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs) can provide solution to these challenges, bridging the gap between data-driven learning and physically grounded control. In their simplest form they only require a single demonstration to be trained and offer several options to adapt the learned trajectory to changes in the environment, such as spatial scaling (adaptability to changes in the initial and goal points), phase stopping or temporal scaling without additional training [17].

Research efforts have been carried out both in the spatial and temporal scaling of DMPs to make the trajectory generation capability more suitable for different scenarios. Recent extensions to the DMP framework have further enhanced its temporal adaptation capabilities and overall

control flexibility. One notable advancement is the reversible DMP formulation introduced in [19], which enables bidirectional trajectory execution, allowing for both forward and backward traversal of a learned motion. This capability is particularly useful in tasks requiring manual backtracking, sensor fault recovery, or human-in-the-loop interventions. The Geometric DMP (GDMP) framework introduced in [20], tackles the challenge of phase dependency in traditional DMPs. GDMP decouples the geometric trajectory from the timing law by parameterizing motion using arc-length rather than time. This phase-independent formulation allows for dynamic control of execution speed, pausing, or reversal without being constrained by the timing of the original demonstration. A limitation of standard DMPs—their inability to respect hard velocity and acceleration constraints—has been addressed in [21]. This work introduces a temporal coupling mechanism, a form of online trajectory scaling that dynamically adjusts the DMP's phase evolution to prevent temporal constraint violations. By proactively scaling traversal speed while preserving the original trajectory path, the method ensures compliance with velocity and acceleration constraints.

In addition to temporal adaptability, DMPs are inherently designed to handle spatial scaling, enabling robots to generalize learned movements to new spatial configurations while preserving the essential structure of the demonstrated trajectory. In their basic formulation, DMPs naturally adjust to changes in the initial and goal positions. Beyond spatial and temporal scaling, DMPs can also be made reactive during execution by incorporating coupling terms into their formulation, which allow the system to respond to external inputs — such as obstacles, or environmental changes — without requiring additional learning. This feature is particularly valuable in real-world robotic applications where adaptability and responsiveness are crucial. A comprehensive literature review on the use and development of coupling terms in DMPs is presented in [11], where various coupling strategies are analyzed and categorized based on their characteristics and the application domains.

However, a critical limitation of DMPs in constrained environments is their inability to ensure trajectory adherence to environmental constraints when adapting to changes in the initial or end points of a task. For example, when the start or goal position is modified, the system may generate trajectories that transgress predefined safety boundaries. This limitation is particularly relevant to our investigation, where environmental constraints define a safety zone, and any transgression of these boundaries compromises operational safety.

D. TRAJECTORY GENERATION AND CONSTRAINT ENFORCEMENT WITH DMPs

When integrating spatial constraints into DMPs, different approaches can be employed to model the trajectory generation process, including machine learning techniques,

constrained probabilistic movement primitives, optimization methods and Artificial Potential Fields (APF). Each method offers distinct advantages and trade-offs in terms of computational efficiency, adaptability, and constraint enforcement. Below, we discuss these approaches in detail.

1) MACHINE LEARNING AND HYBRID APPROACHES

One category of methods uses machine learning, particularly reinforcement learning (RL), to optimize trajectory generation under constraints. For instance, RL-based approaches define reward functions that penalize obstacle collisions [22], [23] or directly optimize DMP parameters for constraint compliance [24]. These methods, although efficient, require large amounts of data to converge. Other hybrid approaches combine DMPs with classical AI techniques. For instance, Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) have been used to model both trajectories and force/torque profiles [25], [26], while Behavior Trees [27] integrate DMPs into high-level task planning frameworks. While these approaches demonstrate the versatility of DMPs in modeling sensory feedback and integrating with high-level planning, they are not tailored for ensuring safe trajectory execution in safety-critical environments.

2) PROBABILISTIC AND OPTIMIZATION-BASED METHODS

Probabilistic Movement Primitives (ProMPs) extend the DMP framework by incorporating probabilistic modeling, enabling the representation of movement variability and adaptation to new situations through environmental constraints [28], [29], [30]. While ProMPs have demonstrated effectiveness in obstacle avoidance and constraint-aware motion planning, they typically require a well-defined and formalized representation of the environment's constraints. However, such information is not always readily available in practice and can be computationally expensive to obtain, limiting their applicability in dynamic or uncertain environments.

Optimization-based approaches [31], [32], [33], [34], [35], [36] formulate constraint satisfaction as an optimization problem, incorporating constraints on position, velocity, and acceleration. These methods often involve minimizing trajectory deviation from demonstrations, ensuring smooth motion, and avoiding obstacles, either in simulation [32], [34], [35] or on real robots [31], [33], [36]. Some formulations integrate DMPs with model predictive control or graph-based optimization to enable real-time adaptation [33], [35]. However, these approaches typically require explicit constraint modeling and computationally expensive solvers, with limited or no quantification of the computational cost.

3) CONSTRAINED DMPs AND ARTIFICIAL POTENTIAL FIELDS

Constrained Dynamic Movement Primitives (CDMPs) [37], [38] extend classical DMPs by incorporating constraints into the weight learning process, using Zeroing Barrier Functions

(ZBFs) to define safety sets in the robot workspace. These safety sets are manually specified by the user and not learned from demonstrations. The CDMP framework optimizes the DMP forcing term via nonlinear programming to ensure the trajectory satisfies the ZBF constraints. However, this approach has two main limitations: it requires manual constraint modeling and offline optimization, which limits its suitability for real-time adaptation.

An alternative approach is to use Artificial Potential Fields (APFs) [9], [11], [39], [40], [41], [42], by introducing a coupling term in the DMP equations to repel the robot from constrained or obstacle-occupied regions. The survey in [11] categorizes DMP-APF combinations into three families: dynamic potential fields, steering angle-based potentials, and alternative approaches. These methods are often used for obstacle avoidance and have been extended to handle joint limits, point obstacles, and manually defined restricted areas.

4) ADVANTAGES AND LIMITATIONS OF APFS

Compared to the previously discussed techniques, APFs add less computational burden, as the DMP framework naturally allows for the extension to potential fields by simply adding the gradient of the field to the acceleration term of the differential equation. This allows for instant computation of the needed forces, enabling real-time adaptation of the DMP trajectory. In obstacle avoidance scenarios, APFs can produce smooth movements while guaranteeing convergence to the desired goal. Moreover, the combination of DMPs and APFs allows adaptation to new situations without relearning, making them attractive for dynamic environments.

Despite these advantages, most existing APF-based approaches either rely on manually defined constraints or require large demonstration sets to learn them [11], which limits their applicability in real-time, safety-critical, or resource-constrained environments. This motivates the development of a more efficient and data-aware approach that can automatically extract and enforce task constraints from a limited number of demonstrations—a key focus of the methodology presented in this paper.

E. METHODOLOGY AND CONTRIBUTIONS

This work focuses on learning from a small number of demonstrations, aiming to reduce the data burden while still capturing the essential variability and constraints inherent in the task. Dynamic Movement Primitives are well-suited for this objective, as they can generalize from a single demonstration. However, by incorporating multiple demonstrations, we aim to extract the natural variability of the task, which provides richer information for defining constraints and improving robustness.

The proposed methodology addresses the challenge of learning manipulation tasks from human expert demonstrations in hazardous and sterile environments. The scenarios

and constraints selected reflect real-world conditions where classical methods, such as standard DMPs, struggle due to strict spatial or environmental constraints. To do so, the proposed technique uses the variability among the demonstrated trials as an indicator of the spatial constraints to respect for executing the task. Based on the methodology introduced in [43], the nominal trajectory is derived from a set of demonstrations and used to train a DMP model. To enforce spatial constraints on the learned trajectory, a novel coupling term is introduced within the DMP framework. This coupling term is activated when the system approaches the safe region's limits defined by the task variability. By incorporating this mechanism, the resulting model can adapt to the current environmental constraints, ensuring that the generated motion remains within the spatial bounds observed in the demonstrations. The DMP representation follows the formulation presented in [9]. This approach is fundamentally a trajectory planning process rather than a real-time control strategy. This differentiates the methodology from virtual fixtures, which enforce constraints in real-time during execution and require immediate feedback loops.

The key contributions of this work are as follows:

- **Automatic Task Constraint Extraction from Human Demonstrations:** A method is proposed to automatically extract task constraints from a small number of human demonstrations, eliminating the need for manual constraint specification. This enables easier robot teaching strategies, particularly for non-expert users.
- **Novel Coupling Term for DMPs (SIG-CDMP):** A novel coupling term for DMPs is introduced to ensure that the generated trajectory remains within the extracted tolerance zone. The coupling term is based on a sigmoidal function, which avoids the generation of large forces and constraint violations that are common in other existing approaches.
- **Ensure Computational Efficiency:** The proposed approach maintains a computational cost comparable to a standard DMPs. This makes it suitable for real-time applications and safety-critical environments.
- **Real-World Industrial Validation:** The proposed method is validated in two real-world industrial applications. The experiments demonstrate that the method successfully generates valid trajectories that respect the constraints, even when adapting to new initial or goal positions.

III. AUTOMATIC TASK CONSTRAINT EXTRACTION

An essential step in our framework is the automatic extraction of spatial constraints from human demonstrations. This ensures that the robot adheres to task-specific boundaries without requiring manual input from the user. In this section,

the method used to extract these constraints from a limited set of demonstrations is described.

A. CONSTRAINT EXTRACTION TECHNIQUE

To illustrate the constraint extraction process, consider the example in Figure 2. It consists of moving the robot tooltip from each of the origins, touching the central white button and moving to the different goal positions. This generates the curves in the Y axis shown in the right part of Figure 2.

FIGURE 2. Setup image (left) and graphical representation of the robot movement in Y dimension (right). Raw trials. The task consists of moving the tooltip from different origins to different goals, but going always through the white button in the middle of the table.

By applying MCA-CDTW (Minimum Cost Averaging Constrained Dynamic Time Warping) [11] a set of warped curves is obtained where it is easily observable that all the curves pass through the same intermediate zone in the vicinity of $Y=0.72m$ in the normalized time period from approximately 2 to 8 s (see Figure 3).

FIGURE 3. Warped trials. At the beginning of the curve we can observe the variability of having different origins, between second 2 and 8 the movement is restricted due to the touching of the white button and at the end of the demonstrations, the variability increases again due to the different goal positions.

From those warped curves, it is straightforward to calculate the mean curve and the variability around it. Figure 4 shows

the nominal (or mean) curve in blue and the tolerance zone given by the variability with the vertical dotted blue arrows. As the variations in the trajectories are relatively small compared to the overall path, we assume that a normal distribution applies to the data. The tolerance zone is therefore calculated using the standard deviation. The standard deviation around the mean includes around 68% of the observations while two standard deviations include 95%, therefore, the tolerance zone, the safe zone where the robot can move, is defined as two standard deviations around the mean.

For uniform or non-normal distributions, the maximum and minimum values of the data in each time-step could instead be used to ensure that the majority of the data falls within the tolerance zone. To capture the true spatial constraints of the task, the human operator should be encouraged to perform a sufficient number of trials that reflect the full range of acceptable motion. In this way the statistical method to identify the tolerance zone (e.g. 2SD) can be thought of as characterizing soft or latent constraints implicitly identified by the operator. New rollouts should tend toward the central values of the demonstrations, but the variability of the demonstrations creates tolerance for deviations away from that nominal solution. When faced with hard constraints, however, the operator should prioritize skirting the edges of the perceived safe zone, and the tolerance zone should be defined as the max and min of those demonstrations. Which formula is used to define the tolerance limits from the data could be set explicitly by the operator, based on their judgment as to whether hard limits need to be respected, or one might automatically choose between the options based on a test of normality of the distribution of the demonstrations.

Figure 4 reveals notable variations in the tolerance zone width throughout the toy example task. Specifically, the permitted movement range is around 50 centimeters at the beginning and end of the task, whereas it narrows to 5 centimeters around second 2, where the white button must be pushed. This fluctuation highlights the limitations of manually setting a fixed static value (e.g., 40cm) which may be suitable for areas where the robot is free to move, but too large for narrower passages, such as the one occurring between seconds 2 and 8. To address this issue, a dynamic approach is proposed, where the threshold is automatically adjusted based on the width of the observed variability obtained from the task demonstrations, thereby ensuring an effective tolerance area extraction. Let W denote the desired percentage of the total width of the tolerance space in which the constrained behavior is activated. The tolerance space is associated with the variability $2SD(i)$ at each time step i . Therefore, the activation zone AZ can be defined at each time step as:

$$AZ = w(i) = W * 2SD(i), \quad i \in [1 \dots N] \quad (1)$$

where N is the length of the trajectory. In this way, MCA-CDTW allows automatically extracting both the task

FIGURE 4. Tolerance zone extracted from the task demonstrations (blue dotted vertical line) is defined as 2SD around the nominal curve (blue curve). The activation zone AZ (gray area) is defined by the user as a percentage of the local tolerance zone ($W = 40\%$ for the generation of this image).

dynamics and its environmental constraints. Assuming that the human is teaching the robot not only the dynamics of the task at hand, but also the task’s geometrical constraints in the environment, the mean curve obtained represents the task to learn and the deviations around the mean, the task constraints, which vary in width according to the human demonstrations.

B. IMPACT OF THE NUMBER OF TRIALS IN THE TOLERANCE ZONE

The reliability and accuracy of the extracted tolerance zone depend on the variability encoded in the demonstrations. Figure 5 shows how the nominal curve and the variability around it depend on the demonstration data. Trajectories presented in Figure 2 are considered. To illustrate the sensitivity to which trials are used, the nominal curve and variability is recomputed after removal of pairs of trials that most significantly alter the nominal curve compared to the original one, as measured by the Mean Absolute Error (MAE). As it can be observed in the figure, the nominal curve remains relatively unchanged. In contrast, the tolerance zone—shown in gray for the original and with dotted lines for the modified versions—demonstrates a stronger dependence on the removed trials. One particular combination significantly reduces the width of the tolerance zone at the end of the trajectory, while the remaining combinations result in only minor and largely similar changes. This highlights the importance of either collecting a comprehensive set of demonstrations or explicitly guiding the user to capture the full range of motion variability and ensure that the tolerance zone accurately reflects the task’s intended behavior.

FIGURE 5. Visualization of nominal curves (solid lines) and the extracted tolerance zone limits (dotted lines) when removing two trials at a time from the full set of demonstrations. The original tolerance zone is shown in gray and the original nominal curve in black.

IV. TEACHING CONTROL POLICIES IN CONSTRAINED ENVIRONMENTS

After extracting spatial constraints and the nominal behavior from human demonstrations, the next challenge is to teach the robot to execute the task while respecting these constraints. This requires the integration of constraint-aware control policies to ensure safe and reliable execution in real-world, often safety-critical, environments. This section first outlines the limitations of standard DMPs in constrained spaces, followed by the introduction of a novel coupling term that enables adaptation to spatial constraints without retraining.

A. LIMITATIONS OF DMPs IN CONSTRAINED SPACES

The nominal trajectory, representing the task, is learned using DMPs. DMPs are composed of a second-order linear dynamical system of type mass-spring damper which attracts the system to the goal, and a non-linear forcing term $f(x)$ that attracts the system towards the demonstrated trajectory [44], [45].

A key feature of DMP models is the ability to cope with changes of initial and goal positions. The generated trajectory is automatically adjusted, without requiring retraining. However, the resulting rollout may violate the tolerance zone derived from the demonstrated variability. This behavior is illustrated in Figure 6. When the initial position is changed (green solid line), the DMP rollout enables to reach the target position. However, the trajectory violates the upper bound of the tolerance zone between seconds 2 and 4, as the DMP formulation does not encode spatial constraints. A similar behavior occurs when changing the goal position, illustrated with the green dotted line. This behavior is undesirable in scenarios where exiting the tolerance zone may lead to interactions with hazardous or unsafe regions.

To address this issue, DMPs are combined with artificial potential fields (APF) to incorporate tolerance zone management into the rollout generation. This requires modifying the

FIGURE 6. Nominal curve (blue) and DMP generated rollout (dotted orange line) coincide as expected. The green solid line is the DMP rollout generated to adapt to the change of origin, which violates the tolerance zone around second two. The green dotted line is the DMP rollout generated to adapt to a goal change, which also violates the tolerance zone between seconds 2 and 8.

DMP equations in [9] by adding a forcing term $\varphi(y)$ derived from a potential field:

$$\tau \dot{z} = \alpha_z(\beta_z(g - y) - z) - \alpha_z(\beta_z(g - y_0)x) + f(x) + \varphi(y) \quad (2)$$

where $\varphi(y)$ is the gradient of the potential function $U(y)$:

$$\varphi(y) = -\frac{\partial U(y)}{\partial y} \quad (3)$$

The potential $U(y)$ is designed to increase as the system approaches the boundary of the activation zone, thereby generating a repulsive force that pushes the trajectory away from the constraint limits. A similar formulation is proposed in [40], referred to as EC-DMP. In this method, the coupling term $\varphi(y)$ is defined as in equation 4 with the variable representation shown in Figure 7:

FIGURE 7. Definition of the safe zone variables in [40], where the activation zone is designed manually.

$$\varphi(y) = \begin{cases} k \left(\frac{1}{y - \bar{y}_l} - \frac{1}{w} \right) \frac{1}{(y - \bar{y}_l)^2} e^{\left(\frac{1}{y - \bar{y}_l} - \frac{1}{w} \right)^2} & y - \bar{y}_l < w \\ k \left(\frac{1}{w} - \frac{1}{(\bar{y}_u - y)} \right) \frac{1}{(\bar{y}_u - y)^2} e^{\left(\frac{1}{w} - \frac{1}{(\bar{y}_u - y)} \right)^2} & \bar{y}_u - y < w \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where k is a constant value.

The coupling term EC-DMP can generate extremely large forces in some circumstances, such as: (i) when the value y is close to the border limits \bar{y}_l (or \bar{y}_u), or (ii) if the activation zone w is significantly smaller than the distance from the system's position to the constraint limits. These limitations are illustrated in Fig. 8, where the EC-DMP is challenged with the new starting point (purple solid line) and new goal (purple dotted line) used in the experiment of Figure. 6. In the new starting point case, the system violates the tolerance limit in the vicinity of second 2 and generates too large forces to complete the task. A similar failure occurs in the goal change case. The system enters the narrower portion of the task, but the repulsion forces are too large. This causes oscillations and even a complete failure of the system, as extremely large forces are generated. Several experiments were conducted to tune the parameter k , but satisfactory trajectory generation was not achieved.

FIGURE 8. Result of applying EC-DMP to the toy example. The purple solid line represents DMP&APF rollout that is generated to adapt to the origin change. The purple dotted curve represents the rollout generated by EC-DMP to adapt to the new goal.

Note that in the DMP rollout process, the temporal integration step dt can affect the reaction time of the system and potentially contribute to the observed overshooting. Indeed, the rollout of the DMP in effect numerically simulates a physical dynamical system consisting of forces acting on a virtual mass. Numerical issues with respect to the

magnitude of the time step used for numerically integrating the system of differential equations arise whenever such a system has highly-stiff forcing terms. But this integrated dynamical system is fictitious and is being used (at least in our case) purely to plan the desired trajectory prior to movement execution. One is not tied to the update frequency of the robot’s control loop. A solution could be to perform the integration with a variable step size in order to avoid the numerical issues. Unfortunately, this did not prove to be effective in our situations. For the curves in Fig. 8, $dt = 0.001$ was used, which is consistent with the standard update frequency for robotic systems. However, reducing dt to as low as 0.0001 did not prevent such failures.

B. A NOVEL COUPLING TERM TO ENFORCE TASK CONSTRAINTS

The EC-DMP [40] is effective in keeping the system within the tolerance zone when the activation zone is constant and the initial position lies within the safe region. However, it exhibits limitations when navigating in narrow passages and/or with small activation widths. To address this, we propose a new coupling term. It is inspired by the Heaviside step function, that varies abruptly from 0 in the safe zone to 1 in the activation zone, but tempered to have a more gradual transition in the interest of smoothness. Two formulations enable a continuous transition from 0 to 1: the hyperbolic tangent and the sigmoidal function. The hyperbolic tangent provides a higher gradient in a more restricted area, while the sigmoid transition is smoother and generates an activation earlier. We chose the sigmoid function due to its earlier response, which reduces the likelihood of generating excessive forces. The coupling term $\varphi(y)$ is defined as follows:

$$\varphi(y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \bar{y}_{u,i} - \bar{y}_{l,i} < \delta \text{ mm} \\ \beta \frac{1}{1 + e^{\left(-\frac{k}{w_i}(\bar{y}_{l,i} - y_i)\right)}} & y_i - \bar{y}_{l,i} < w_i \\ -\beta \frac{1}{1 + e^{\left(-\frac{k}{w_i}(y_i - \bar{y}_{u,i})\right)}} & \bar{y}_{u,i} - y_i < w_i \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

being k and β constant values, w_i the width of the activation zone in each timestep i and $\bar{y}_{u,i}$ and $\bar{y}_{l,i}$ the upper and lower bounds in each timestep i respectively. This function becomes active when the trajectory position y_i enters the activation zone defined as a distance w_i from the lower ($\bar{y}_{l,i}$) or upper ($\bar{y}_{u,i}$) constraint boundaries at each time step i . The amplitude of the coupling force is scaled by the constant β , which determines the magnitude of the correction applied to the DMP. The steepness of the transition near the constraint boundaries is controlled by the ratio $\frac{k}{w_i}$: a larger ratio results in a sharper transition, making the function behave more like a step function, while a smaller ratio yields a smoother, more gradual response. When the width of the tolerance zone is very narrow ($< \delta$), the potential is deactivated to avoid

the oscillations due to the conflicting repulsing forces of very close tolerance zone walls. This potential deactivation capability will ensure the adherence to the learned behavior in the narrow passages over the corrections of the potential.

To highlight the differences between EC-DMP and SIG-CDMP coupling terms, we have plotted both forces for different constant width sizes. We have established the upper bound as $\bar{y}_u = 3$ and the lower bound as $\bar{y}_l = 1$. For both formulations k has been set to 1, and we use the different width sizes $w = [0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6]$. Additionally SIG-CDMP uses $\beta = 250$. Figure 9 presents the response of both forces for each width value (solid lines EC-DMP and the dotted lines SIG-CDMP). Analyzing the response of EC-DMP (solid lines in Fig. 9), it is observed that for wider activation zones, the force exhibits a gradual increase before turning to infinity. However as w decreases, the force $\varphi(y)$ spikes to infinity abruptly, which is an undesirable behavior. In contrast, SIG-CDMP (dotted lines in Fig. 9) exhibits a more consistent response to the width change. Due to the mathematical form of the sigmoid force function, it increases rapidly at the beginning, transitioning to a smoother behavior as the system goes closer to the limits and eventually saturating at β . For small widths, it is observable that it rapidly saturates to β . This formulation ensures a rapid initial push away from the activation zone, while avoiding singularities in the trajectory generation due to infinite forces. Since β is a tuneable parameter, the coupling term can be adapted to the specific needs of the different tasks.

FIGURE 9. Comparison between the EC-DMP (solid lines) and SIG-CDMP (dotted lines) forces for static task limits $\bar{y}_u = 3$ and $\bar{y}_l = 1$ and different widths $w = [0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6]$.

1) SIG-CDMP IN GENERAL SPACES

Figure 10 shows the comparison between EC-DMP, SIG-CDMP and classical DMP applied to the toy example where the tolerance zone is still wide (around 5 cm) in its narrowest zone. It can be observed that the green curves that represent the classic DMP rollouts (both solid and dotted)

violate task constraints. As previously discussed, in both scenarios, EC-DMP is not capable of generating a complete trajectory, as points of the rollout fall out of the task limits. In contrast, rollouts generated with SIG-CDMP (cyan lines) move smoothly away from the activation zone, complying in every moment with the tolerance zone.

FIGURE 10. Comparison between the rollouts generated using EC-DMP (in purple), SIG-CDMP (in cyan) and classical DMP (in green). The solid lines represent the rollouts generated to adapt to the new origin and the dotted curves represent the rollouts generated to adapt to the new goal.

2) SIG-CDMP IN NARROW SPACES: CONTEXT-AWARE GOAL ADAPTATION

Potential fields are known to produce oscillatory behaviors in narrow passages [46]. Figure 11 illustrates the variability in X dimension of a cable wiring task. As shown, between seconds 2 and 18, the width of the tolerance zone is very narrow (less than 1mm around second 5), requiring the robot to follow a tightly constrained path. To address this challenge, we use the DMPs’ capability to adapt to a new goal position online. Similar to the idea of delayed goal function presented in [47] or the via-goals in [48], we propose a context-aware goal adaptation strategy. This strategy modifies the goal position during rollout generation in two phases:

- Phase 1: The DMP begins by generating a rollout that adapts to the new initial point while maintaining the goal defined by the nominal trajectory learned during the training phase. The DMP starts generating the rollout towards the original goal to ensure smooth movement within the narrow passage, aligning with the nominal behavior.
- Phase 2: Once the trajectory exists the narrow region, the goal is dynamically updated to the new desired target position. This allows the DMP to generate a smooth, goal directed motion for the remainder of the task.

This strategy maintains the original trajectory’s dynamics while avoiding oscillations in narrow zones, and nevertheless ensures convergence to the new goal. We propose the

FIGURE 11. Comparison between the rollouts generated using context-aware goal adaptation SIG-CDMP (in cyan) and context-aware goal adaptation DMP (in orange). The solid vertical line represents the goal adaptation time instant.

term “context-aware” in this work to refer to the system’s ability to dynamically adapt its behavior based on the task-spatial constraints. The “context” is defined by the operational environment (e.g., extremely narrow tolerance zones in industrial settings), and the “awareness” refers to the automatic detection of when the robot must enter and exit those zones. This enables the system to autonomously adjust the instant of the goal change without requiring explicit user intervention.

To determine automatically the goal transition point (i.e. the moment when the system exits the narrow passage) and safely transition to the new goal, a function analyzes the vertical distance between the upper and lower bounds of the tolerance zone in each dimension. The function identifies the narrowest point and detects the first instance where the width increases steadily over a 50 ms window. If multiple narrow sections are detected along the trajectory, the one closest to the goal is selected to ensure the transition occurs at the appropriate spatial context. This index marks the moment when the passage starts to widen, indicating that the robot has exited the critical narrow section and can safely transition to the updated goal position (which is represented with a solid vertical line in Figure 11).

Note that the effectiveness of the context-aware approach depends on the choice of APF-based coupling terms. As shown in Figure 11, the context-aware goal adaptation with a classical DMP (orange curve) fails to converge rapidly to the nominal trajectory, resulting in the inability to enter inside the

narrow passage. In contrast, the proposed SIG-CDMP (cyan curve) generates a trajectory that cleanly enters the narrow zone and follows the nominal path.

The coupling terms in DMPs introduce an external force to guide motion within spatial constraints, but in extremely narrow passages, this force can conflict with the learned dynamics of the nominal trajectory. The coupling terms can still create spurious oscillating behaviors as the virtual mass “bounces” back and forth between the activation zones. This conflict causes oscillations as the system struggles to balance the learned motion and external guidance. For extreme narrowness where the width of the tolerance zone is smaller than δ (being $\delta = 1mm$ in our setups), we therefore deactivated the coupling term to prioritize adherence to the learned dynamics. This modification eliminates oscillations, as evidenced by the cyan curve in Figure 11. By deactivating the coupling term when the tolerance width falls below δ , the system relies solely on the learned dynamics (from training), leveraging the DMP framework’s inherent stability to navigate narrow zones without oscillations.

The improved performance of the SIG-CDMP over standard DMPs is not limited to narrow passages but is analytically grounded in the mathematical structure of the potential function (Equation 5) and the system’s dynamics. The coupling term $\varphi(y)$ in Equation 5 is designed to smoothly transition between active and inactive states, ensuring that external forces are applied only when necessary. Specifically:

- **Deactivation in extreme narrowness** ($\bar{y}_{u,i} - \bar{y}_{l,i} < \delta$) removes destabilizing forces, allowing the system to rely solely on the learned dynamics, which are inherently stable due to their derivation from a trained trajectory.
- **Sigmoidal activation** in wider regions ($y_i - \bar{y}_{l,i} < w_i$ or $\bar{y}_{u,i} - y_i < w_i$) introduces a bounded, smooth force field that guides the system toward a safe zone without abrupt changes, minimizing oscillations. This hybrid design balances adaptability to constraints with the stability of the nominal trajectory.

3) LYAPUNOV STABILITY

Building on the work of Rai et al. [49] and Huang et al. [40], the Lyapunov stability of the DMP model extended with the proposed coupling term is evaluated. Considering equation 2, when $t \rightarrow \infty$, the phase variable x tends to zero, as well as the forcing term. Hence equation 2 is reduced to:

$$\tau \ddot{y} = \alpha_z(\beta_z(g - y) - \dot{y}) + \varphi(y) \quad (6)$$

which can be simplified as:

$$\ddot{y} = K(g - y) - D\dot{y} + \varphi(y) \quad (7)$$

being K and D the stiffness and damping matrices respectively (both symmetric and positive definite).

The Lyapunov function V is constructed using the energy function of a damped spring mass system:

$$V(y, \dot{y}) = \frac{1}{2}(g - y)^T K(g - y) + \frac{1}{2}\dot{y}^T \dot{y} + U(y) \quad (8)$$

differentiating $V(y, \dot{y})$ yields:

$$\dot{V} = \nabla_y V^T \dot{y} + \nabla_{\dot{y}} V^T \ddot{y} \quad (9)$$

$$\dot{V} = -[(g - y)^T K \dot{y} + \dot{y}^T \varphi(y)] + \dot{y}^T \ddot{y} \quad (10)$$

Replacing eq. 7 in the above expression, it becomes:

$$\dot{V} = -[(g - y)^T K \dot{y} + \dot{y}^T \varphi(y)] + \dot{y}^T [K(g - y) - D\dot{y} + \varphi(y)] \quad (11)$$

and being K symmetric and positive definite, $(g - y)^T K \dot{y} = \dot{y}^T K(g - y)$. Therefore the expression can be simplified as:

$$\dot{V} = -\dot{y}^T D \dot{y} \quad (12)$$

Hence, $\dot{V} < 0$, which complies with the stability criteria and indicates that the additional term does not compromise the stability of the system.

4) COMPLETE PROCESS FLOWCHART

Figure 12 shows the complete flowchart proposed for few shot task learning. The process can be divided into two main blocks: *skill learning* and *skill generation*.

On the *skill learning* block, the nominal curve is obtained by averaging the set of teleoperated demonstrations of the task using MCA-CDTW. The nominal curve is then used to train a DMP. The environmental constraints of the task are extracted by calculating two standard deviations around the nominal trajectory (the tolerance zone) or by using the min/max values per timestep depending on the chosen strategy.

Once the movement primitives are learned and the tolerance and activation zones calculated, the *skill generation* block is enabled. If the system is set to follow the learned average trajectory, the coupling term will be null as the system always remains within the safe zone, and the DMP will follow the learned path without violating the task constraints. However, when choosing a new origin or target position, as shown with the toy example, the DMP may generate curves that violate the task constraints. The system checks if the curve enters the activation zone and, if true, the potential generates a repulsive force to move the system away from it, until it is no longer inside the activation area. This check is done per dimension, applying the force only in the dimension(s) that may cause the violation of the task constraints. The final generated (rollout) trajectory will be therefore inside the tolerance extracted from the demonstrations.

V. EXPERIMENTS

To evaluate the performance of the proposed coupling term in real-world applications, two industrial use cases were selected: sterility testing in the pharmaceutical industry and cable wiring in electric car batteries. The experiments were designed to assess the validity, smoothness, and computational efficiency of the proposed method (SIG-CDMP) compared to the baseline (EC-CDMP) and classical DMP.

FIGURE 12. Graphical description of the flowchart of the proposed process, illustrating the key steps involved, including the task constraint extraction and the SIG-CDMP coupling term proposed.

A. EVALUATION METRICS

The following metrics were used to assess the performance of the generated trajectories:

- Rollout Validity (RV): The generated rollout is considered valid if and only if all dimensions fall within the tolerance zone. If not, RV will be false.
- Smoothness cost (SC): Measures the smoothness of the generated rollout. It is based on the Dimensionless Jerk which is represented by the jerk cost defined as [50]:

$$SC = \frac{D^3}{v_{peak}^2} \int_{t=0}^{t=T} \left(\frac{d^3 r(t)}{dt} \right)^2 \quad (13)$$

where $\left(\frac{d^3 r(t)}{dt} \right)^2$ is the squared jerk, D is the duration of the demonstration and v_{peak} is the demonstration’s peak speed. A lower smoothness cost indicates a smoother rollout.

- Curve generation cost (CGC): The computational cost required (in seconds) to calculate a rollout curve.

B. USE CASE 1: STERILITY TESTING IN THE PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY

This task focuses on automating a manual process in the pharmaceutical industry, the sterility testing process. This process involves testing a liquid for potential contamination. One key step in this process is to transport the bottle to a holder as it can be observed in Figure 13.

This subtask is required to allow the liquid transfer from the bottle to the pumping machine. To create the dataset, a teleoperation platform was used. The platform featured a haptic device (sigma.7, Force Dimension, Switzerland) on the leader side, which was used to remotely control a robotic arm (UR5, Universal Robots, Denmark) equipped with an industrial gripper (2F-140 Robotiq, Canada). The recording sampling frequency was 1KHz.

An expert operator demonstrated the task six times, with the bottle placed at different initial positions and the holder at different target positions. To test the generalization capability of the method, 15 new initial points and 15 new goal points

FIGURE 13. Setup for bottle to holder task demonstration.

were generated, evenly distributed within the tolerance zones of the start and target regions. From these, 150 initial–goal pairs were selected for evaluation, specifically those that caused the classical DMP rollout to exceed the tolerance zone in at least one of the three dimensions (X, Y, Z). For each pair, trajectories were generated using EC-CDMP, SIG-CDMP, and classical DMP, and evaluated using the metrics defined above.

C. USE CASE 2: CABLE WIRING IN ELECTRIC CAR BATTERIES

This task focuses on automating the cable routing in electric vehicle battery assemblies. After connecting one end of the cable to the connector, the cable must navigate through a certain passage without touching sensitive battery

components. This process requires precise spatial constraints to ensure that the safety of the battery and operator is not compromised. This task is particularly challenging due to the required precision in different parts of the movement as it can be observed in Figure 14, where the cables have free space to move both in zones 1 and 3 (start and target zones respectively), but the robot’s movement has to be precise along zone 2.

FIGURE 14. Electric car battery. (Left) The three numerated zones with yellow rectangles around represent the different zones of the task demonstration: 1) start zone; 2) constrained zone; 3) target zone. The three dotted lines represent the 3 demonstrations performed by the user (in blue, red and green). (Right) Zone 2 zoomed. It is mandatory for all the cables to be placed inside the constrained zone.

To create the dataset, three human demonstrations were recorded using a teleoperation platform. The robotic arm (UR10e, Universal Robots) was equipped with a gripper. The demonstrations started with the cable connector positioned at a fixed location (different terminals on the battery module) in the area marked with zone 1 in the figure and varied in the final connection points (three distinct goal positions) in the area marked with a 3 in the figure to capture the spatial variability of the task. Demonstrations were recorded at 1 kHz, with the operator guiding the cable through the narrow passage in the zone 2 and avoiding structural supports of the battery. These three demonstrations are shown with dotted lines in Figure 14. All the data processing was done on an Intel Core i7-13850HX, 32GB RAM with Python 3.10 in a Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS machine.

1) RESULTS ON THE STERILITY TESTING TASK

With the experimental setup and process flow established, the results of the proposed techniques on the industrial task are analyzed. The recorded trials were warped using [11], producing the aligned data shown in Figure 15. The variability observed is varying depending on the dimension and the instant in time. This is demonstrated in Figure 16, which shows the estimation of the activation area, following the method described in section III.

FIGURE 15. Warped trials in X,Y,Z dimensions for the bottle to holder task.

FIGURE 16. Tolerance zone in X,Y,Z dimensions extracted from the warped demonstrations. The tolerance zone is the area between the red lines and the gray are is the activation zone, that represents 40% of the total variability in each timestep. The nominal curve is represented in blue.

The activation zone was calculated $W = 40%$ (in equation 1). The parameter k for EC-DMP was set to 0.005 (in equation 4). The parameters $\beta = 500$ and $k = 2$ were used to tune SIG-CDMP (equation 5). For this use case, the general approach for the SIG-CDMP in general spaces was used as there is no extreme low variability zone.

Table 1 summarizes the results obtained according to the three evaluation metrics (rollout validity (RV), smoothness cost (SC), and curve generation cost (CGC)). The mean

and variance values of smoothness cost (SC) and curve generation cost (CGC in seconds) are reported for the generated trajectories, while the rollout validity (RV) is expressed in total count of valid trials. SC and CGC were calculated only for valid rollouts.

The rollout validity analysis reveals that EC-DMP produced only 6 valid trajectories out of 150 requests, indicating poor constraint adherence. This failure was particularly pronounced in scenarios where the starting point lay within the activation zone or when the system approached narrow tolerance zones. In such cases, the coupling forces generated by EC-DMP pushed the trajectory beyond the tolerance bounds. Different orders of magnitude were tested for k providing similar results (the generated curves were different but invalid anyway). On the contrary, the proposed SIG-CDMP approach was capable of generating 150 out of 150 curves inside the tolerance zone without the need to modify the constant parameters. Classic DMP was not able to generate any rollout inside the constrained region.

The curve generation cost for classic DMP averaged 1.191 seconds per rollout, with minimal variance (0.0002) and standard deviation (0.014). This low variability indicates consistent, predictable performance across all 150 samples, making DMP well-suited for real-time applications requiring reliable trajectory generation. When introducing the new forcing term, it can be observed that none of the techniques suffered from it in terms of curve generation cost. Both EC-DMP and SIG-CDMP techniques had a slightly higher mean curve generation cost (1.208 seconds and 1.206 seconds respectively). This represents an increase of approximately 0.8%, which cannot be considered a burden for the curve calculation. Despite the small increase, both EC-DMP and SIG-CDMP showed very low variance and standard deviation, making the curve-generation cost consistent again among the generated curves.

As expected, classical DMP produced smoother trajectories than EC-DMP and SIG-CDMP. This outcome aligns with the design of classical DMP, which avoids perturbing the natural trajectory flow with additional acceleration terms. The low variance and standard deviation for the smoothness cost demonstrate that the classical DMP algorithm was consistent on generating predictably smooth trajectories, which is crucial for robotic applications. SIG-CDMP technique had a moderate mean smoothness cost. The variance and standard deviation were moderate too, suggesting that the smoothness of the trajectories has some variability but is generally consistent across the 150 samples. On the contrary, EC-DMP exhibited a very high mean smoothness cost, which indicates that the generated trajectories were significantly rough. Besides, its extremely high variance and standard deviation suggest a large variability in the smoothness of the trajectories. This variability implies that while some trajectories may be smooth, others are very rough, which can be problematic for applications requiring consistent smoothness.

The following images show two different situations. The first case (Fig.17) illustrates a scenario where the tolerance zone is sufficiently wide along the entire path, allowing both EC-DMP and SIG-DMP to generate valid rollouts successfully. In contrast, the second case (Fig.18) demonstrates a situation where the tolerance zone becomes slightly narrower in certain sections. While SIG-DMP adapts to these tighter constraints and succeeds, EC-DMP fails to navigate the reduced clearance. In both figures, only the Y and Z axis are shown, as the generated rollouts do not violate the tolerance zone in the X dimension.

In Figure 17 it can be observed in the zoomed areas how both coupling terms (EC-DMP in purple and SIG-CDMP in cyan) made the rollouts navigate inside the tolerance zone while the classic DMP's rollout violated the tolerance zone. In this case, the response of both coupling terms was similar.

TABLE 1. Mean, standard deviation and variance of smoothness cost of the curve generation cost and smoothness cost of the rollouts obtained after processing the database. SIG-CDMP provides smooth overall results. Count is the number of trials out of the 150 requested. DMP is not able to generate any valid rollout while SIG-CDMP has generated 150 valid trajectories. (RV = Rollout Validity, CGC = Curve Generation Cost, SC = Smoothness Cost).

Metric	Technique	Count	Mean	Variance	SD
RV	DMP	0	-	-	-
	EC-DMP	6	-	-	-
	SIG-CDMP	150	-	-	-
CGC	DMP	150	1,191	0,0002	0,014
	EC-DMP	6	1,208	0,0001	0,013
	SIG-CDMP	150	1,206	0,0002	0,014
SC	DMP	150	0,084	0,0002	0,013
	EC-DMP	6	2131,17	4470298,8	570,6
	SIG-CDMP	150	2,8026	7,8246	2,797

Figure 18 illustrates a case with a narrower activation zone, where the EC-DMP generates forces so high that the rollout generated a position far out of the tolerance zone. In the Y dimension (upper image), both techniques generated appropriate rollout. In the Z dimension, in particular in the narrowest zone, the EC-DMP (purple line) curve went outside the graph (it has been cut for a better visibility since the generated point had the order of $1e^{78}$).

Regarding the high difference in the smoothness cost of EC-DMP compared to SIG-CDMP, Figure 19 shows the reason behind it. When the coupling term gets activated, EC-DMP makes the rollout's response more aggressive generating sudden changes in the trajectory (see the purple line inside the zoomed area). These jumps have a considerable impact on the smoothness.

To assess the impact of tuneable parameters (k , β , and W) on trajectory smoothness, a systematic parameter sweep was conducted. For each combination of k , β , and W , 150 trajectories were generated, and the smoothness cost was calculated as a quality metric. The results, summarized in Table 2 and Figure 20, reveal how these parameters influence trajectory smoothness, with mean and standard deviation reported for each configuration. For visibility purposes,

FIGURE 17. Representation of a situation where both EC-DMP and SIG-CDMP were capable of generating curves inside the tolerance zone (Y,Z dimensions). EC-DMP is represented in solid purple and SIG-CDMP in dotted cyan.

FIGURE 18. Representation of a situation where EC-DMP is not capable of generating curves inside the tolerance zone (Y,Z dimensions). Orange curve represents the classical DMP, EC-DMP is represented in purple and SIG-CDMP in cyan.

the range of β values tested is shown instead of each value. As shown, increasing β leads to a consistent rise in

FIGURE 19. Comparison of the generated curves in Y dimension in a situation where the smoothness cost of EC-DMP is very high compared to SIG-CDMP. EC-DMP is represented in purple and SIG-CDMP in cyan.

the mean smoothness cost, indicating a stronger influence of the coupling term and a greater deviation from the natural, unconstrained DMP trajectory. Similarly, increasing W results in higher mean smoothness costs, as a wider activation zones introduce larger trajectory adjustment to satisfy constraints. Regarding k , higher values result in a sharper activation of the coupling force, which localize the correction to a narrower region around the constraint. This minimizes unnecessary adjustments to the trajectory and reduces the deviation from the original DMP path, leading to a lower smoothness cost. In contrast, a smaller k results in a more gradual coupling force, spreading the correction over a wider range and introducing more variation in the trajectory, which increases the smoothness cost.

TABLE 2. Smoothness cost statistics for different parameter combinations in the sterility testing task.

k	W	β (range)	mean (min–max)	SD (min–max)
1	20	25–350	0.17–15.95	0.19–32.26
1	25	25–350	0.17–20.36	0.15–37.47
1	30	25–350	0.27–27.41	0.34–51.65
1	40	25–350	0.34–42.87	0.41–63.41
2	20	25–350	0.08–3.38	0.02–6.20
2	25	25–350	0.09–4.73	0.04–8.90
2	30	25–350	0.10–6.59	0.04–11.62
2	40	25–350	0.11–11.94	0.05–17.89

2) RESULTS ON THE CABLE WIRING IN ELECTRIC CAR BATTERIES

Following the methodology, the first step was to extract the task constraints. Using MCA-CDTW, the variability in the demonstrations was analyzed to define the tolerance zone around the nominal trajectory. In critical scenarios like this one, where exceeding the tolerance zone is strictly prohibited, the tolerance zone was defined using the maximum and

FIGURE 20. Three-dimensional visualization of the mean smoothness cost as a function of the coupling parameters k , β , and the width of the activation zone W . Each point represents a different parameter configuration, with color and size encoding the mean value. The plot illustrates the nonlinear and multivariate dependence of trajectory smoothness on these parameters.

minimum values extracted from the warped demonstration curves at each time step, rather than the 2-standard-deviation (2SD) probabilistic approach. This method ensures the robot’s trajectory remains within the absolute extremes observed in the demonstrations, guaranteeing strict constraint adherence. The results of applying MCA-CDTW to extract the tolerance zone are shown in Figure 21, where narrow zones between seconds 2.5 and 18 in the X dimension are evident (below 1mm in this dimension). Due to these narrow constraints, the context-aware goal adaptation strategy was applied.

FIGURE 21. Tolerance zone in X,Y,Z dimensions extracted from the warped demonstrations. The tolerance zone is the area between the red lines and the gray area is the activation zone, that represents 20% of the total variability in each timestep. The nominal curve is represented in blue. Extreme narrow zones appear in X dimension.

A 0.5 mm deviation threshold was established to evaluate trajectory validity, based on industrial robotic applications where sub-millimeter precision is critical for functional integrity and system reliability. This threshold defines the maximum allowable deviation from task constraints. To test robustness, 20 starting positions were selected where the natural DMP trajectory violated the 0.5 mm threshold. Deviations below this threshold were considered negligible for task compliance.

The EC-DMP method failed to generate achieve the goal for all 20 start positions due to the large generated forces in the narrow passages. In contrast, the context-aware goal-adaptive DMP reached the goal for all tested points but still violated the tolerance zone. This highlights a key limitation: while the pure context-aware goal-adaptive DMP ensures trajectory generation and convergence to the goal, it does not guarantee full compliance with tight constraints without an additional coupling term.

Figure 22 illustrates a representative example of how the context-aware goal adaptation SIG-CDMP is capable of adapting to a new origin located in the external area of the initial tolerance zone ($k = 2, \beta = 100$, and $W = 0.20$). The context-aware goal adapting SIG-CDMP (cyan line) effectively pushes the trajectory away from the task limits, allowing a clean entrance inside the extreme narrow area in the X dimension. Once the narrow zone has a width of $\delta < 1mm$ the coupling term is deactivated in order to avoid oscillations and ensure the adherence to the learned dynamic obtaining smooth trajectories inside the constrained area. In contrast, the context-aware DMP (orange line) violates the tolerance zone at the entrance. In the Y dimension, two shorter narrow zones were handled adequately by both methods without oscillations. Here, the wider tolerance zone allowed the context-aware goal-adaptive approach to comply with constraints, unlike the X dimension.

Table 3 summarizes the smoothness cost (SC) statistics for different parameter combinations (k , β , and W). For clarity, results of the tested $\beta = [25 - 450]$ values (incrementing each time in 25) have been grouped, showing minimum and maximum mean SC values. Note that not all β values produced valid rollouts for every start point, so statistics are computed only from valid trials. A comprehensive visualization of all parameter configurations is provided in Figure 23.

TABLE 3. Smoothness cost statistics for different parameter combinations in the cable wiring task.

k	W	β (range)	mean (min-max)	SD (min-max)
1	20	25-450	2.09-10.53	0.01-1.27
1	25	25-375	4.73-179.52	0.00-6.56
1	30	25-25	11.18-11.18	0.03-0.03
2	20	25-450	2.06-4.75	0.02-1.10
2	25	25-175	2.83-16.73	0.01-0.08
2	30	25-75	4.38-15.59	0.01-0.03

(a) Results in the X dimension of the cable wiring task.

(b) Results in the Y dimension of the cable wiring task.

FIGURE 22. Tolerance zone in the X and Y dimensions in the cable wiring task. The context aware goal adaptation is used for the DMP (in orange) and SIG-CDMP (in cyan) curve generation. The vertical line represents the time instant when the goal is updated.

Regarding the influence of the parameters k , β , and W , the same tendency as in the sterility test use case is observed. The results reveal that β (coupling strength) exhibits a strong positive correlation with the smoothness cost (the bigger the SC, the rougher the trajectory): at low β values (typically <350), SC remains moderate, but sharp spikes occur beyond $\beta = 350$. This effect is amplified when combined with low k (activation sharpness), as $k = 1$ produces extreme SC spikes at high $\beta > 350$ (yellow dots in Fig. 23), while $k = 2$ stabilizes SC. This happens because bigger k localizes corrections in the trajectory to narrower regions, minimizing unnecessary adjustments and therefore generating smoother trajectories. Activation zone width (W) directly elevates SC by requiring larger trajectory adjustments to satisfy constraints as wider activation zones imply higher probability to activate the coupling term. Besides, higher W also reduces the number of valid rollouts in extremely narrow spaces, as overly broad activation zones may violate constraints. For new use cases, the parameter configuration of $\beta = 100$, and $W = 20$ with $k = 2$ serves as a stable baseline, balancing

FIGURE 23. Three-dimensional visualization of the mean smoothness cost as a function of the coupling parameters k , β , and the width of the activation zone W . Each point represents a different parameter configuration, with color encoding the mean value. The plot illustrates the nonlinear and multivariate dependence of trajectory smoothness on these parameters.

moderate SC and constraint compliance, though further optimization may be needed for task-specific requirements.

Notably, these parameter adjustments did not affect the curve generation cost. The curve generation cost mirrored the previous use case: on average, SIG-CDMP required 0.8 seconds per trajectory, compared to 0.74 seconds for the standard DMP, reflecting a marginal computational overhead.

VI. CONCLUSION

Teaching by demonstration is a lofty goal that promises to make the programming of robots much more efficient. In its simplest form, teaching by demonstration involves demonstrating to a robot what is the trajectory to be followed. But to be robust and flexible, we assert that the ultimate goal should be to teach the robot control policies that can be used to generalize from the demonstration case to reality in a variable environment. The development of DMPs to execute the learned trajectory was already a step in that direction, providing a means to generalize to new target locations. However, a persistent challenge in real-world robotic applications lies in ensuring that robots not only learn trajectories but also enforce environmental constraints without requiring extensive training data or manual intervention. This study directly addresses this gap by developing a framework that enables non-expert users to teach robots by combining the automatic extraction of task-specific spatial constraints from a limited number of human demonstrations with a constraint-aware trajectory generation strategy based on Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs) and Artificial Potential Fields (APF). The framework’s ability to infer constraints autonomously and enforce them during the path planning phase, with no computational burden, marks a significant step toward making robotic learning more

intuitive, accessible, and applicable to complex real-world tasks.

The contributions of this work are threefold. First, the framework introduces a method for automatic constraint extraction, using MCA-CDTW to temporally align the recorded demonstration. Once aligned, the variability among the trials is used to define the tolerance zone. This eliminates the need for manual constraint specification, significantly reducing user workload and enabling non-expert operators to teach robots in safety-critical environments. Second, a novel coupling term (SIG-CDMP) is proposed to enforce constraint adherence of the DMPs. Unlike existing methods such as EC-DMP, which suffer from singularities and large accelerations, the sigmoidal potential field-based coupling term ensures smooth, reproducible motion even in extreme narrow passages, avoiding oscillations and constraint violations. Third, the methodology is validated in two real-world industrial applications demonstrating its efficacy. The proposed method has proven to maintain the computational efficiency of the classic DMPs while generating smooth reproducible trajectories inside the constrained space. Together, these contributions enable a robust trajectory planning method for intuitive automation in complex, safety-critical scenarios.

While the current implementation assumes static 3D constraints derived from demonstrations, future work will extend the framework and integrate orientation restrictions for full 6-DOF control. Additionally, we aim to explore techniques (such as RL, optimization methods or predictive control methods) to generate the optimal curve from point A to point B that does not violate the tolerance zone extracted from the demonstrations and compare it to the curves generated by our DMP&APF approach. We also seek to extend the proposed method to function as a real-time controller, shifting its role from trajectory planning to direct actuation inside a control loop.

This work advances the field of robotic learning from demonstration by addressing the unresolved challenge of constraint-aware trajectory generation in real-world applications. The proposed framework combines intuitive human demonstrations with rigorous constraint enforcement, enabling robots to learn control policies that respect inferred geometrical constraints without retraining. This combination, marks a step toward intuitive robot programming, suited for automating real-world complex tasks.

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